

Case Studies in Music Production for Advanced 3D Audio Reproduction with Bottom Channels

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ABSTRACT

This research report describes the production of several immersive musical sound scenes for a 9+10+8 (27.2) 3D audio reproduction system. 9+10+8 features an even spatial distribution of loudspeaker channels in three vertical layers: top (above the listener), main (ear-level), and bottom (below the listener). 3D sound recording and mixing methodologies are discussed with reference to four specific sound scenes: solo jazz piano, large pipe organ in a concert hall, alternative rock, and a taiko drum ensemble, as well as in more general terms within the realm of music production for 3D audio systems. This report aims to help fill a current gap in published knowledge surrounding music production for 3D audio systems featuring bottom-layer reproduction channels, such as NHK 22.2, Sony 360 Reality Audio, and various binaural audio production and rendering mediums.

0 INTRODUCTION

Numerous commercial and broadcast 3D audio formats have been introduced, many of which have been standardized by the International Telecommunications Union (ITU) [1]. These audio formats aim to increase the user's sensation of realism, envelopment, and presence, as well as improve localization of real and virtual sound sources being reproduced from all around the listener. 3D sound-fields can be reproduced using either an array of loudspeakers, or over headphones using binaural rendering [2]. In either case, an optimal presentation of a 3D sound scene would include sound reproduction from all around the listener: not just at head-height, but also from above and below, as with real-life listening. Several currently available 3D audio formats, such as NHK 22.2 Multichannel Sound and Sony 360 Reality Audio, already include bottom-layer loudspeaker-based sound reproduction. Meanwhile, binaural audio rendering

tools theoretically allow for the panning of sound sources to any location in the horizontal or vertical plane.

Although a number of researchers and content creators have introduced concepts or techniques for 3D music recording and reproduction, much of this work has focused exclusively on how to capture audio for elevated "height channels," i.e., loudspeakers placed above the listener [2, 3]. Comparatively few authors have discussed music production techniques optimized for 3D audio reproduction systems including "bottom channels," i.e., loudspeakers placed at or near floor-level. A great deal of both direct and reflected sound in our daily lives comes from below us and is an important part of real-life listening; sound from below in 3D audio reproduction is a valuable area of research that remains largely unexplored. This report describes several case studies in audio production of musical sound scenes for a 9+10+8 (27.2) 3D audio reproduction system. The sound capture

techniques cover methodologies and aesthetics ranging from simple “recreative aesthetic” microphone configurations to complex hybrid recording systems and mixing schemes designed specifically for non-classical music.

1. BACKGROUND

1.1 9+10+8 (27.2) audio reproduction

All recordings described herein were recorded for a custom 9+10+8 (27.2) 3D audio reproduction system. Following the ITU’s naming convention for advanced audio systems [1], 9+10+8 refers to a reproduction system with nine height channels, ten “main layer” channels (loudspeakers placed roughly at ear-level), and eight bottom channels. 9+10+8 is identical to 9+10+3 (also known as NHK 22.2 Multichannel Sound) [4] in terms of number and spatial positions of loudspeakers, but adds bottom channels for the Side Left and Right, and Rear Left, Centre, and Right speaker positions (Fig. 1). The addition of the five bottom channels gives an even spatial distribution of loudspeakers in all three vertical layers, which allows for the potential to create highly realistic or hyper-realistic presentations of various 3D sound scenes.

Figure 1: 9+10+8 channel/loudspeaker physical layout. Channel nomenclature as per ITU [1].

1.2 Music production techniques for 3D audio

Numerous techniques for capturing acoustic music for 3D audio reproduction have been discussed, many of which are

described within Lee's [3] extensive review of multichannel 3D microphone arrays. These techniques tend to be optimized for use with smaller-scale 3D audio formats, such as 4+5+0 or 4+7+0, but their design concepts are easily adaptable to larger-scale formats. Within Lee's review, only two techniques specifically include microphones for bottom layer loudspeakers: “Hamasaki et al.” [5] and “Howie et al.” [6]. Both techniques are optimized for “concert” perspective sound scene reproduction, using widely spaced directional microphones to capture ambient sound, and either directional (Hamasaki) or omnidirectional and directional (Howie) microphones to capture the direct sound of the ensemble. Grew et al. [8] describe a variation on the “OCT-9” [9] 3D microphone array with three spaced directional microphones added to capture sound specifically for bottom channels. Eaton and Lee [10] describe a variation on Lee’s PCMA-3D microphone array, adding three spaced directional microphones 30 cm above the floor, facing away from the sound source, to capture sound for the bottom layer.

A review of the above mentioned sources reveals several trends for the selection and positioning of “bottom channel” microphones: 1) using microphones with directional sound pickup characteristics (e.g., cardioid or hypercardioid polar patterns), 2) placing these microphones within 1 m of the floor, 3) having a significant vertical spacing between the bottom layer and main layer microphones (typically greater than 1 m), 4) facing these microphones towards the sound source or ensemble (except for Eaton and Lee), usually with somewhat of a downward facing angle (e.g., -30°). Similar methods have also been observed in 3D music recording setups used by NHK and WOWOW broadcast recording engineers. The use of directional microphones for bottom channels is particularly important: it ensures a focus on direct and reflected sound coming naturally from below within the sound scene, thereby capturing sonic information that has a

logical spatial relationship with the floor-level loudspeakers that will be reproducing it.

Within non-classical music production for 3D audio with bottom channels, Howie [11], and Martin and King [12] have described various concepts and considerations for recording and mixing pop and rock music for 9+10+3 reproduction. Additionally, Martin and his co-authors [13–15] have shown that complex close-microphone arrays can be used to capture and reproduce the direct sound of an instrument in a way that yields stable sonic images with perceivable horizontal and vertical extent. When these techniques are combined with ambience arrays to capture room reflections, it is possible to create pop/rock sound scenes that deliver a high degree of realism or hyper-realism, and inform the listener of the relationship between the performer and the performance space: a methodology described in detail in [11]. Another benefit of using such an approach is that it allows the recording engineer to capture a more complete representation of a given instrument’s timbre profile. Most musical instruments have complex, frequency-dependent sound radiation patterns [16]. A multichannel close microphone array that extends both horizontally and vertically will naturally capture a more realistic impression of an instrument than what is possible when using only one or two close microphones, as is typical with stereo or 5.1 music production techniques.

2. 3D MUSIC RECORDING CASE STUDIES

All recordings described herein were recorded at 96kHz/24bit resolution, by a team of recording engineers and 3D audio researchers possessing a combined 50+ years’ experience recording or mixing multichannel audio, and a combined 25+ years’ experience recording or mixing 3D audio. Recordings were mixed for 9+10+8 reproduction in Studio B at Tokyo University of the Arts' Senju Campus. The room is equipped with 27 “KS Digital C5” full-range 2-way

powered studio monitors. Speaker positions conform to ITU recommendations for 9+10+3 reproduction [1], with the five added bottom channels matching the horizontal angles of their corresponding main-layer speakers.

2.1 Case study 1: solo jazz piano

A solo jazz piano performance was recorded in Studio A at Tokyo University of the Arts' Senju Campus: floor area = 160 m² ceiling height = 7 m, reverb time = approx. 1.0 s at 500 Hz. A Steinway concert grand piano was placed in the north end of the room, facing to the south: the south end of the room being somewhat more acoustically resonant than the north end, with a greater density of reflections. An array of nine cardioid microphones, arranged as Left, Centre, and Right in three vertical layers, was placed near the piano to capture primarily direct sound (Figs. 2–3). Placement was designed to capture and reproduce an image of the piano that was realistic in terms of timbre and physical extent, based on similar techniques described in [11] and [17]. The bottom channel microphones were placed specifically to capture both direct and reflected sound from underneath the piano: a perspective that has a darker, more bass-heavy tonality than what is captured with more traditional piano microphone placements. Microphone signals were assigned directly to their corresponding loudspeaker channels (Table 1), except for the “close top layer” microphones, which were panned between the top and main layers. The resultant piano image retains a natural impression in terms of size, shape, and timbre.

An array of largely spaced directional microphones was set up to capture ambient sound for the height-layer speakers, and side and rear main-layer and bottom-layer speakers (Figs. 2–3, Table 1). Ambience microphones were generally placed at least 2 m apart to ensure a high level of decorrelation between signals [18]. This large number of ambience signals panned in three vertical layers provides the listener with a

realistic and enveloping impression of the sonic characteristics of the recording venue. All microphones were routed to either ADT or RME microphone preamplifiers, then to Digital Audio Denmark (AX32) analog to digital converters. Microphone signals were balanced and panned to give the listener an impression of standing approximately 1.5 m in front of the piano: a fairly close sound that retains enough depth perspective and ambience for a strong sense of space around the music. Artificial reverb (Flux IRCAM verb) was added to certain ambience channels to somewhat lengthen and smooth the recording venue's reverb tail.

Table 1: Microphones for solo piano

Placement	Microphone	Polar Pattern
Piano TpL	Schoeps MK6	Cardioid
Piano TpC	Schoeps MK4	Cardioid
Piano TpR	Schoeps MK6	Cardioid
Piano L	Schoeps MK4	Cardioid
Piano C	Schoeps MK4	Cardioid
Piano R	Schoeps MK4	Cardioid
Piano BtL	Schoeps MK21	Wide Cardioid
Piano BtC	Sony C38	Cardioid
Piano BtR	Schoeps MK21	Wide Cardioid
Ambience BL	AKG c414-XLII	Wide Cardioid
Ambience BR	AKG c414-XLII	Wide Cardioid
Ambience BC	AKG c414-EB	Cardioid
Ambience SiL	AKG c414-XLII	Cardioid
Ambience SiR	AKG c414-XLII	Cardioid
Ambience TpFL	DPA 4011	Cardioid
Ambience TpFR	DPA 4011	Cardioid
Ambience TpFC	DPA 4011	Cardioid
Ambience TpC	Schoeps MK41	Hyper Cardioid
Ambience TpBL	Sennheiser 8040	Cardioid
Ambience TpBR	Sennheiser 8040	Cardioid
Ambience TpSiL	Sennheiser 8040	Cardioid
Ambience TpSiR	Sennheiser 8040	Cardioid
Ambience TpBC	DPA 4011	Cardioid
Ambience BtBL	Sony C100	Cardioid
Ambience BtBR	Sony C100	Cardioid
Ambience BtSiL	AKG c414-ULS	Cardioid
Ambience BtSiR	AKG c414-ULS	Cardioid
Ambience BtBC	Neumann U87i	Cardioid

2.2 Case study 2: pipe organ in a concert hall

This example comes from a set of recording sessions for a stereo release of solo pipe organ music, recorded at Tokyo University of the Arts' Sōgakudō Concert Hall, an 1100 seat classical music venue (length = 36 m, width = 18 m, height = 15 m) with a variable reverb time that was set to

Figure 2: Piano microphone placement, overhead view

Figure 3: Piano microphone placement, side view

approximately 2.4 s for this recording. The microphone setup used was a combination of a “Decca Tree” [19, 20] with outriggers, and a Left-Centre-Right array of “close” microphones, all optimized for stereo reproduction. Additional microphones in both “main” and “ambient” positions were then added to create a 3D audio recording (Table 2, Figs. 1, 4–5).

The FLc, FC, and FRc omnidirectional microphones were fitted with acoustic pressure equalizers [21] for improved channel separation at higher frequencies, as in [6]. Since the pipe organ is such a physically large instrument, all of the “front” microphones captured a good deal of direct sound. When these signals are assigned to their respective loudspeakers, the resultant sonic image of the organ extends downward vertically from the top layer of speakers nearly to the floor, and spans around 100–120° in width. Ambience microphones were generally spaced at least 2 m apart horizontally and vertically. Microphone signals were routed to a Studer Vista 5 console for preamplification and analog to digital conversion. As the organ pipes do not extend all the way to the stage, the bottom channel microphones were positioned facing upward (+45°), capturing a fairly equal blend of direct and reflected sound. In this way, when combined with the main and height layer front microphones, the bottom channel signals do not “pull” or “smear” the sonic image of the organ any lower than how it would be perceived when listening in the concert hall. Due to time and equipment constraints, microphones were not placed for the following channels: TpC, TpBC, BC, BtBC.

This recording makes use of a number of omnidirectional microphones, particularly in the main layer, which were chosen based on the sonic goals for the stereo recording, and a desire to effectively capture the organ's rich low frequency content. Directional microphones were used for all bottom channel locations, to allow for better precision in capturing specific aspects of the lower sound scene. Placement of all microphones was based largely on previous experience recording in Sōgakudō, availability of microphone hanging and patch points, and in-situ listening during rehearsal and soundcheck. Most microphone signals maintain a linear relationship between label and panning, e.g., the “FL” microphone is assigned directly to the “Front Left” speaker. The exceptions are the three “close” microphones signals,

which were panned 50% between the main and top layers. Thus, the close presence within the sound of the organ is weighted more towards the upper part of the sonic image, which corresponds to the mixing engineer's impressions from listening to the organ at various locations within the concert hall. Artificial reverb was applied to a number of ambience channels to lengthen the reverb tail (Altiverb 7: King's College), giving the mix a more cathedral-like sound that is typical for pipe organ music.

Figure 4: Organ microphone placement, overhead view

Figure 5: Organ microphone placement, side view

Pairs of “high”, “mid”, and “low” perspective close microphones captured the basic image of the drum kit, which were then combined with other close microphones to complete the sound image. Pairs of vertically spaced close microphones were used for both the kick and snare drums, which aids in achieving more accurate vertical localization and “spread” for those instruments within the mix [11]. The bass amp close sound was captured with 4 directional microphones (centre, bottom, left, right), spaced ~25–35 cm apart. The “main guitar” close image is a composite sound from two different combo-amplifiers: a Peavy Bandit placed on top of a Roland Jazz Chorus (Fig. 8). Four microphones, arranged as Top, Centre, Left and Right, were placed near the Bandit, while two more microphones were placed near the stereo speakers of the Jazz Chorus. While the Bandit close microphones were panned to retain a realistic image size and focus for the guitar amp sound, the Jazz Chorus signals were panned widely to the BtSiL and BtFC speakers, resulting in a guitar image that expands horizontally and vertically in a somewhat triangular shape (Figs 6–7). The vocal was captured with a five-microphone spaced array: left, centre, right, top, bottom, with signal panning largely following those conventions. Approximately 70 cm further back from this set of microphones was a “Blumlein” pair of ribbon microphones, which were delayed and assigned to the BL and BR channels to create an immersive echo effect.

A number of widely spaced directional microphones were setup to capture ambient room sound throughout the recording sessions (Fig 9). This microphone array remained largely unchanged regardless of which instrumental part was being recorded, though the number and physical positions of microphones varied depending on the desired level and quality of ambience for a given instrument, as well as considerations to time delays between microphone signals.

Figure 8: “Main guitar” amp and microphone setup

Figure 9: Rock drums, from behind, with ambience microphones

Once the primary parts of the musical arrangement had been recorded, it was felt that there was enough sonic information within the 9+10+8 environment to give the listener a strong sense of presence. Thus, the remaining instrumental parts could often be recorded with simpler microphone setups, while still achieving desired the physical, timbral, and textural characteristics. The “chorus guitar” part was recorded through the Roland Jazz Chorus, with three close microphones (BL, BC, BR) and two distant microphones. The distant microphone signals were panned to the TpFL and

TpFR speakers, and delayed by 240 ms, creating a vertical echo effect. For each of the monophonic synthesizer parts, the direct signal was routed to a combo guitar amplifier, with one ribbon microphone placed near the amp, and another several meters away. When these pairs of signals are assigned to loudspeakers that face each other on a diagonal (e.g., TpFR and BtBL), a sense of depth and spaciousness within the sound scene is achieved, especially when multiple monophonic parts panned to different spatial locations are being performed at the same time. The piano was recorded with three pairs of microphones set up successively further and higher away. Three microphones were placed close to the acoustic guitars at “bright”, “neutral”, and “dark” sounding positions, which were then assigned to the TpSiL/R, SiL/R, and BtSiL/R right channels respectively, creating tall, column-like guitar images. The tambourine was captured only with ambience microphones in order to give the instrument a highly diffuse sound image.

Within the primary instruments of the musical arrangement, panning of microphone signals to the bottom layer was largely based on the desire for those instruments to localize in a way that reflects real-life listening. For example, the two kick drum microphone signals are panned and balanced to localize the image of the kick drum mostly in front of and below the listener. In contrast, the bass “8ve synthesizer” parts in the song’s chorus were panned to the bottom layer for purely aesthetic reasons. In general, the mix engineer tried to construct a sound scene wherein the more diffuse and “airier” sounds localized above the listener, mid-range instruments localized nearer to ear level, and low frequency elements localized more towards the bottom layer (Fig 7). This approach was inspired by personal aesthetics, but also a desire to respect the well documented “pitch-height” metaphor within human hearing [22–26].

Compared with the complexity of capturing these sound images, the mixing process was simpler. As has been

described anecdotally by many other practitioners recording or mixing for large-scale 3D audio environments, dynamic range compression was found to be largely unnecessary, and was only used sparingly to even out the dynamics within the lead vocal performance. EQ, when needed, was largely subtractive, removing unwanted or masking resonances.

Rather than using existing multichannel or “3D” algorithmic reverb tools, mono instances of reverb plugins would be inserted directly on ambience channels, adjusting the wet/dry mix, balance of early and late reflections, timbral properties, and reverb time of each channel until a desirable multichannel ambience was achieved. This method gave the mixing engineer greater control over the spatial aspects of ambience within the mix than what they had found to be possible with available 3D reverb plugins.

2.4 Case study 4: taiko drums

A recording was made of a taiko drum ensemble (one 大太鼓 [ōdaiko] and two 締め太鼓 [shime-daiko]) in the above-described Studio A. To ensure focused direct sound images of the drums, the performers were positioned in the least acoustically resonant area of the room, with large sound absorbing baffles placed approximately 2 m behind each of the instruments (Fig. 10). Ambience microphone placement prioritized capturing a greater density of reflected sound for the side and rear channels. For this recording, a simple one microphone per loudspeaker setup was used (Table 3). The direct sound of the three instruments was captured by a set of eight microphones, corresponding to the FL, FLc, FC, FRc, FR, BtFL, BtFC, and BtFR channels. For the FLc, FC, and FRc channels, omnidirectional microphones were used to ensure a linear capture of low frequencies from the ōdaiko. Placement of the bottom channel microphones focused on capturing the sound coming off the bottom of the three drums, as well as early reflected sound from the floor. Careful balancing of the main and bottom layer close microphones

results in a sonic image of the drums that accurately reflects both the horizontal and vertical locations of the instruments in the room.

Most of the horizontal microphone positions remained relatively unchanged between vertical layers (Fig. 10). The primary exception is the three rear bottom microphones: the recording team found that when placed at the same distance as the main and top-layer microphones, the rear bottom microphones contributed an unpleasant ambience to the recording that blurred the impact of the large ōdaiko drum, particularly in the low frequencies. By moving those microphones closer to the instruments and facing them towards the ōdaiko, a better balance between direct and diffuse sound was achieved in the lower layer. Microphone input routing followed the same signal path as for Case Study 1. Once a satisfactory balance had been achieved between all microphone signals, low or low-mid frequency filtering was applied to certain ambience channels to increase focus and definition within the transients of the drums. Artificial reverb (LiquidSonics' Seventh Heaven) was applied sparingly to a number of ambience channels to lengthen and smooth the reverb tail in a way that better matched with the musical intentions of the performers.

3 DISCUSSION

3.1 Some considerations and observations for music production with bottom channels

Music mixing strategies used by contemporary audio engineers are largely based on concepts and techniques developed for stereo audio production. Stereo is a format that, when compared with real-life listening, suffers from a great deal of spatial, tonal, and timbral compression of sounds and sound scenes. Equalization, dynamic range reduction, and level automation are tools commonly used by engineers to help “fit” the various sounds of a group of instruments into the limited spatial environment of the stereo field.

Table 3: Taiko microphones

Placement	Microphone	Polar Pattern
FL	Austrian Audio OC 818	Cardioid
FR	Austrian Audio OC 818	Cardioid
FC	Schoeps MK2H	Omnidirectional
FLc	Schoeps MK2H	Omnidirectional
FRc	Schoeps MK2H	Omnidirectional
Ambience BL	Schoeps MK21	Wide Cardioid
Ambience BR	Schoeps MK21	Wide Cardioid
Ambience BC	DPA 4011	Cardioid
Ambience SiL	DPA 4011	Cardioid
Ambience SiR	DPA 4011	Cardioid
Ambience TpFL	Sennheiser 8040	Cardioid
Ambience TpFR	Sennheiser 8040	Cardioid
Ambience TpFC	Sennheiser 8040	Cardioid
Ambience TpC	Schoeps MK41	Hyper Cardioid
Ambience TpBL	Schoeps MK4	Cardioid
Ambience TpBR	Schoeps MK4	Cardioid
Ambience TpSiL	Schoeps MK4	Cardioid
Ambience TpSiR	Schoeps MK4	Cardioid
Ambience TpBC	Sennheiser 8040	Cardioid
Ambience BtFC	Neumann U87	Cardioid
Ambience BtFL	Neumann U87	Cardioid
Ambience BtFR	Neumann U87	Cardioid
Ambience BtBL	AKG c414-XLII	Cardioid
Ambience BtBR	AKG c414-XLII	Cardioid
Ambience BtSiL	AKG c414-XLII	Cardioid
Ambience BtSiR	AKG c414-XLII	Cardioid
Ambience BtBC	Neumann U87	Cardioid

Figure 10: Taiko microphones, overhead view. Height of layers: 71–87 cm (Bottom), 157–170 cm (Main), 367 cm (Top).

3D audio formats, particularly large-scale formats such as 9+10+3 and 9+10+8, offer vastly more spatial resolution than stereo or 5.1 “surround sound,” allowing engineers more options and choices in terms of building individual sound images, ambient sound fields, and complete musical sound scenes. When the sonic images of various musical instruments can be constructed (or re-constructed) and positioned in physical space in a way that gives an impression approximating real-life (or beyond) listening, the use of EQ and dynamic range compression becomes far less important than in stereo production, allowing the engineer to use those tools for more artistic or aesthetic reasons. This was found to be particularly true for the Alternative Rock case study, where the spatial positioning of “background” or “secondary” instrumental parts helped inform their role within the arrangement and mix without having to reduce their level, tonal presence, or position within the mix’s depth perspective. Also, the final mix required relatively little level-automation of the various instrumental parts – unusual for a rock recording with a dense arrangement.

While examining the perceptual influence of floor level-loudspeakers, Grewe et al. [8] found “that the addition of the lower layer loudspeakers is particularly recognizable and beneficial for content containing floor-related signals, such as footsteps.” This is interesting to consider in tandem with Eaton and Lee’s [10] experiment where subjects were asked to balance three vertical playback layers of four different recordings made for 9+10+3 reproduction. For the “orchestra” example, subjects generally balanced the bottom layer signals higher than for other recordings under test. The microphone signals assigned to the orchestra recording’s bottom channels contained a mixture of direct sound from the strings and early floor reflections, which Eaton and Lee hypothesize “might have been found [by subjects] to be more useful to create a more realistic sound field in the 9+10+3 reproduction.” [10] These conclusions are in line with the

authors’ experience creating the recordings described herein. The presence of direct and early reflected sound in the bottom layer seems to contribute to a greater sense of presence and realism within the sound scene, whereas overly diffuse or reverberant bottom channel information, even in the rear channels, can at times contribute to a general lack of clarity.

Extensive experience recording and mixing music for various 3D audio formats with bottom channels has led to this observation: multichannel direct-sound objects whose microphone signals are anchored to several adjacent loudspeakers in the horizontal and vertical planes can produce sound images whose localization within the 3D sound space is stable regardless of most listener positions within the reproduction environment. What does tend to change as the listener moves around the playback environment, away from the “sweet spot,” is the instrument’s timbre and perceived depth within the sound scene: an experience similar to real-life listening.

3.2 Evaluation of recordings

Several informal evaluations of these recordings have taken place in 3D audio production studios at Tokyo University of the Arts, Kyushu University, and McGill University. Listeners have included professional recording engineers, researchers in the field of 3D audio, and graduate students in audio production. Generally, the recordings have been well received, particularly the Alternative Rock and Taiko recordings, both of which seem to impart a very strong sense of “being there” to the listeners. One professional listener said this of the Alternative Rock recording: “The moment the first drum break hits, you know exactly where you are, exactly what the room is like.” When considered with the observations and previous work discussed in Section 3.1, this may suggest that effective use of bottom channels within 3D audio reproduction can contribute to a greater ease of what Baldwin calls “auditory space perception” – “The ability to

develop a spatial representation of the world (or the area one is experiencing) based on auditory information." [27]. This would be interesting to investigate further in a controlled experiment.

Some listeners felt that the organ recording lacked a certain degree of clarity and power within the direct sound of the instrument. This may be related to the large number of omnidirectional microphones used for ambience capture within the concert hall. Although these microphones were spaced far enough apart for their signals to be mostly or completely decorrelated, it is possible that with omnidirectional ambience microphones, there is still too much acoustic reflected information shared between signals. When the various time delays between microphones are factored in, this may contribute to a sense of muddiness or confusion within the recording, which could be abated by using directional microphones, particularly for the side and rear ambience channels.

3.3 Critical testing material

For accurate perceptual audio evaluations and experiments, critical material that stresses the systems under test is necessary [28]. The recordings described herein were created partially as experiments in advanced audio production, and partially to help fulfill the need for 3D audio materials that meets this "critical" standard. Excerpts of these recordings are currently being used as part of the stimuli sets for several 3D audio experiments at Tokyo University of the Arts, Rochester Institute of Technology, and McGill University, and will also be made available to other researchers.

4. CONCLUSION

This preprint describes the production of four musical sound scenes for a 9+10+8 advanced 3D audio reproduction system: solo jazz piano, pipe organ in a concert hall,

alternative rock, and taiko drums. The immersive audio production techniques described herein are based on extensive previous experience recording for multichannel and immersive audio systems, and previous research in 3D audio content creation. It is hoped that this report can help serve as a guide to other content creators producing work for immersive audio systems including bottom-layer sound reproduction. As "critical testing material", these recordings are currently being used as stimuli in several 3D audio experiments at universities in Japan, Canada, and the U.S., and will be made available for use by other researchers upon request.

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